

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF OPTIMIZING THE CONTENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of optimizing the content of preschool education, focusing on didactic approaches, competency-based components, and factors that enhance pedagogical technologies. The study provides a systematic analysis of designing child-centered educational content, the use of active learning methods, ICT integration, play-based learning, and the development of an enriched educational environment. Scientific and practical recommendations are proposed to modernize the preschool education curriculum and improve the quality of the didactic process in accordance with contemporary standards.*

Keywords: *preschool education, content optimization, didactic opportunities, pedagogical technologies, developmental environment.*

Introduction

Modernization of the content of the preschool education system, improvement of its didactic foundations and enrichment with modern approaches are considered one of the priority areas for improving the quality of education today. The psychophysiological development, cognitive processes, and socio-emotional formation of preschool children should be combined not with the old-fashioned interpretation of the content, but with an optimized, scientifically based, competency-oriented educational model. In this regard, the study of the didactic possibilities of optimizing the content is of theoretical and practical importance. The process of optimizing educational content in the preschool education system is closely related to the creation of educational experiences that are appropriate to the age characteristics of children, scientifically based and increase efficiency. The main goal of optimization is to relieve the educational process of overload, focus on the formation of basic competencies, and improve the quality of educational and developmental activities. Reconsideration of content based on didactic principles Optimization of educational content is based on the fundamental principles of didactics. These include scientificity, systematicity, consistency, age-appropriateness, and practice-orientedness. Restructuring the content based on these principles helps children master the most important knowledge and skills, appropriate to their cognitive abilities:

1. Using an integrative approach Interdisciplinary integration in preschool education is an effective means of optimizing content. Combining areas such as speech development, mathematical imagination, creativity, and environmental education forms a holistic worldview in children. Through integration, repetitive content is reduced and the educational process becomes natural and interesting.
2. Educational technologies based on game activities Preschool age is a stage when the game is the leading activity. Didactic games, a developing environment, interactive methods facilitate the educational process, make it possible to convey complex concepts in a simple and interesting way. This increases the level of effectiveness of the content.

3. Individualized Approach Opportunities The optimization process takes into account the developmental pace, interests, and individual needs of each child. A differentiated approach helps to adapt educational content, reduce overload, and naturalize the developmental process.
4. Use of digital tools and multimedia Information technologies serve to modernize the content of preschool education. Multimedia lessons, interactive games, and digital resources combine visual, audio, and kinesthetic perception, making the learning process easier and more effective.
5. Improving the assessment of learning outcomes Formative assessment, observation, and portfolio-based analysis methods help determine the real effectiveness of educational content. Content optimization is achieved more sustainable results when carried out in harmony with assessment results.

In the process of revising the content of education and updating it in accordance with state programs and standards, the effectiveness of education, the system of methods, the set of competencies, and pedagogical technologies are analyzed as a whole. In this regard, theoretical approaches developed by leading psychologists and pedagogical scientists, as well as the requirements of the modern educational environment, are being studied in depth [1; 12-p].

Theoretical and methodological foundations of optimizing the content of preschool education The content of preschool education is a set of pedagogical mechanisms that ensure the intellectual, speech, social, emotional and physical development of the child, which is inextricably linked with didactic foundations, principles, methods, game technologies and a developing environment.

Scientific review of the concept of optimization Optimization is the process of organizing the educational process in the most effective way, reducing overloads, structurally correct formation of content, and coordination of tools and methods. The main goal of this process is to create content that is adapted to the development of the child, interesting, effective and psychologically comfortable [2; 44-p].

Didactics defines the components of preschool education content: purpose, content, methods, means, forms. Their combination increases the effectiveness of optimization. Basic didactic principles: systematicity, relevance, person-centeredness, continuity, integrativeness, practical orientation [3; 27-p].

Preschool education serves as the basis for the development of the child's basic competencies. It develops at later stages of education, as well as throughout life. The state curriculum is based on a competency-based approach. It is aimed at developing competencies that are formed in various types of children's activities in the process of preschool education and upbringing. Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, abilities and values of a child. A competent child can mobilize and apply his knowledge, skills and abilities in a specific situation, achieve his goal and solve age-appropriate tasks at each stage of development. The competency-based approach to teaching preschool children involves developing children's ability to effectively respond to cognitive needs, problems, and opportunities, develop moral norms and values, communicate with other people, and form a personal identity (the concept of "I").

Communicative competence - requires the possession of constructive methods and means of interaction with people around; the ability to communicate and successfully solve the arising game, cognitive, household and creative tasks. This competence also includes the development of speech. Speech is a necessary tool for the child's cognitive and social development and knowledge

of the world. In a content-rich and stimulating educational environment, children develop oral and written communication skills, which help them to trust themselves, establish relationships with others, form their understanding of the world, participate in activities and complete project work in a team. Children can express themselves in order to be understood by adults and other children. They listen and observe to understand what is said; hear questions and tasks and respond accordingly. They positively view activities involving speech, especially reading and writing. They know the different forms and functions of speech, use them and, if necessary, adapt them in different communication situations. This competence also includes the ability to independently use various communication tools and channels to obtain information; it strengthens the ability to search, analyze and select the necessary information for use in learning and development, to organize, transform, and store it.

Social competence is the child's ability to work together with peers and adults, adhering to established rules of conduct and etiquette. Children learn to respect others and take into account what they say. They follow the rules of behavior necessary for effective work in groups. In problem situations, they take actions to resolve them in accordance with their age and individual developmental characteristics. They increasingly see themselves as part of a group and understand that they have rights and responsibilities. They are open to individual differences. Children can live in harmony with others. They communicate with different people and recognize the cultural diversity of those around them, can help them and support them.

Personal competence (creation of the concept of "I"). Through the development of personal competence, the child demonstrates a number of characteristics that are formed in preschool age and continue to improve throughout life. This competence includes the child's ability to take responsibility for self-care, as well as the skills to manage his daily life and implement a sustainable healthy lifestyle. Children know their place in life, learn to take care of their own well-being, as well as the well-being of others. The child is independent and confident in himself. He knows his strengths and weaknesses, begins to work on eliminating them. He understands how he is different from others. Can put forward and promote their own ideas; learns to make decisions for themselves. Shares their hobbies, interests, and feelings. Meets their growing physical, cognitive, emotional, and social needs. Expresses their needs and knows how to satisfy them, can control themselves; adheres to the rules of a healthy lifestyle, cultural and hygienic rules, engages in physical education, and shows responsibility for their own health.

Cognitive competence includes the ability to acquire knowledge, read and learn; to independently search, analyze and select the necessary information to understand the world around them. Through movement and interaction, children develop strategies for acquiring knowledge and learning. They explore and discover new objects in the world around them. In the process of playing and interacting with others, they observe and experiment. They find new opportunities to understand and solve problems. They share their discoveries and gradually become independent, self-directed, analytical and creative individuals. Children can focus on solving problems, develop strategies for solving problems and use their cognitive abilities to set goals to understand and explain the world around them. Children can continue their interest in learning, enjoy learning and share what they have learned, share their discoveries with others. Cognitive activity is a personal characteristic expressed in independence and interest in the world around them, aimed at transforming social experience. The development of cognitive activity occurs in the process of thinking and perception and is determined by qualitative changes and indicators. A child with

energetic energy is interested in activity, shows diligence in cognition, determines the results of activity in the process of meaningful learning, cultural aspects of the situation [4; 61-p].

Conclusion

Play is the main form of development in preschool age. When educational content is integrated with game activities: the child thinks independently, develops social competencies, forms communication skills, and increases motivation. Therefore, game technologies are one of the most important tools for optimizing content [5; 38-p]. It serves as an effective basis for modernizing the content of preschool education by widely using ICT and digital resources on a normative basis, strengthening the competency-based approach based on modern standards, enriching the developing environment with diverse materials, introducing an integrative education model, increasing the methodological training of teachers, using game activities as a central didactic tool, and effectively organizing the expansion of resource provision on the basis of public-private partnerships.

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